

International Environmental Law: Issues and Concepts

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Abstract

Many natural resources and their environmental components are ecologically shared. The use by one state of natural resources within its territory will invariably have consequences for the use of natural resources and their environmental components in another State. This is evident where a river runs through two or more countries or living resources migrate between two or more sovereign territories. Innocent activities in one State may, such as release of CFCs, have significant effects upon the environment of other States or on areas beyond national jurisdiction. Thus ecological interdependence poses a fundamental problem for international law and explains why international cooperation and the development of international environmental standards are increasingly indispensable. The challenge for international law in the world of Sovereign States is to reconcile the fundamental independence of each State with the inherent and fundamental interdependence of the environment.

Keywords: Environment, Precautionary Principle, Sustainable development, Pollution

Introduction

Human activities in most part of the world are transforming the global environment. Among the numerous factors that contribute to global environmental change, mention can be made of land-use change, desertification and deforestation, loss of biodiversity, air pollution, ozone depletion and climate change. Changes in average and extreme patterns of weather and climate are capable of putting vital resources under pressure. Ecosystems become more susceptible to the emergence, invasion and spread of opportunistic species.

The early international legal developments which addressed aspects of the conservation of natural resources have crystallized into an important and growing part of public international law. The conditions which have contributed to the emergence of international environmental law are two-fold:

1. Environmental issues are accompanied by recognition that ecological interdependence does not respect national boundaries; and that
2. Issues previously considered to be matters of domestic sovereign concern have international implications: The implications which may be bilateral, sub regional or global can frequently only be addressed by international law and regulation.

The growth of international environmental issues is reflected in the large body of principles and rules of international environmental law which apply bilaterally, regionally and globally and reflects international interdependence. The progress in developing international legal control of activities has been gradual, piecemeal and often reactive to particular incidents or availability of scientific evidence. It was not until the late 19th century that States began to recognize the transboundary consequences of activities which affected shared waters or led to the destruction of wild life (such as fur seals) in areas beyond national jurisdiction. In the 1930s the transboundary consequences of air pollution were acknowledged in Trail Smelter case. In 1950s the international community legislated on international oil pollution in oceans. By 1970s, the regional consequences of pollution and destruction of flora and fauna were obvious and, by 1980s, global environmental threats were part of international community's agenda as scientific evidence identified the potential consequences of ozone depletion, climate change and loss of biodiversity. Local issues were recognized to have transboundary, then regional and ultimately global consequences.

The UN Conference on Environment and Development

The UN Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED), 1992, provided an opportunity to prioritize environmental issues and consolidate a vast and unwieldy patch work of international legal commitment. The treaties and other international measures adopted prior to and at UNCED reflect the growing range of economic activities which are a legitimate concern of international community and properly subject to international regulation. UNCED agreed priorities could be divided into two categories:

- a) those relating to protection of various environmental media, and
- b) those relating to regulation of particular activities or products.

The first category identified priorities for the protection and conservation of particular environmental media as :

- a) Protection of atmosphere in particular by combating climate change, ozone depletion and ground level and transboundary air pollution.
- b) Protection of land resources;
- c) Halting deforestation.
- d) Conservation of bio-diversity;
- e) Protection of fresh water resources; and
- f) Protection of oceans and seas (including coastal areas) and marine living resources.

The second category of major issues identified products of human, technological and industrial innovations, which are considered to be particularly harmful to environment requiring international regulation. These are the management of:

- a) Biotechnology;
- b) Toxic chemicals, including their international trade;
- c) Agricultural practice;
- d) Hazardous wastes, including their international trade;
- e) Solid wastes and sewage related issues; and
- f) Radioactive wastes.

For both categories the international legal issues are complex and cannot be considered or addressed without taking into account political, cultural, economic and scientific concerns. For instance:

- a) What level of environmental protection should the standards seek to establish?
- b) Should the standards be set on a uniform basis or should they be differentiated to take account of political economic and ecological circumstances?
- c) What regulatory and other techniques exist to apply the standards?
- d) How are the standards to be enforced domestically and internationally? and
- e) What happens if a dispute arises over non-compliance?

In addressing these questions, it is clear that the environment is a complex system of interconnections, that to understand the evolution and character of a particular environment it is necessary to consider a broad range of apparently unrelated factors, and that these factors should be understood as interacting with each other in a number of ways which do not permit them to be treated as discrete. The interdependence of environmental issues poses legal challenges: How to develop and apply a comprehensive and effective set of legal requirements aimed at preventing environmental damages by addressing the source without taking measures which will cause harm elsewhere. Current efforts to develop environmentally sound energy policies reflect that challenges and require international law making to respond to environmental complexity.

Influence of Non-Legal Factors On International Environmental Law

International environmental law is influenced by a range of non-legal factors. The likelihood of achieving an international agreement increases with:

- a) Greater scientific consensus about causes and seriousness of a problem;
- b) Increased public concern.

- c) Perception on the part of negotiating States that other partners are doing their fair share to address the problem;
- d) Increase in short term political benefits;
- e) Existence of previous related multinational agreements.

Factors which lessen the likelihood of reaching an international agreement include:

- a) Upward costs of environmental control, and
- b) Increase in the number of States negotiating a treaty

Of all these factors, two are particularly influential:

- a) Impact of science, and
- b) Impact of economics.

Given that the land, seas and the air space of planet earth are shared, and given that world — transforming activities, especially economic activities, can have effect directly or cumulatively on large parts of the world environment, how can international law reconcile the inherent and fundamental interdependence of the world environment? How could legal control of activities adversely affecting the world environment be established, given that such activities may be fundamental to the economies of particular states?

Precautionary Principle

The precautionary principle requires that if there is a strong suspicion that a certain activity may have environmentally harmful consequences, it is better to control that activity now rather than to wait for incontrovertible scientific evidence. Precautionary Principle provides a basis for action to be taken in the event of scientific uncertainty. The 1985 Vienna Convention and its 1987 Montreal Protocol, the 1990 ban on dumping of sewage sludge in the North sea and the 1992 Climate Change Convention can be cited as examples of international environmental regulations being adopted in the face of scientific uncertainty and in the absence of international consensus on the existence of environmental harm.

Precautionary Principle was for the first time invoked before the ICJ in the Nuclear Tests case brought by New Zealand against France. The French government responded that the legal status of the principle was “uncertain”. So did the UK, when the Principle was invoked by the European Commission as a reason for precautionary trade restrictions against the risk of mad cow disease.

Precautionary Principle and Indian Law

The Indian Judiciary actively supports the Precautionary Principle. In the judicial pronouncement of **Vellore Citizens Welfare Forum v. UOI**, AIR 1996 SC 2715 the Supreme Court opined that sustainable development is the need of the hour. The court emphasized on the fact that there should be a balance between economic growth and protection of the environment. The Court rejected the traditional concept that ecology and development are opposed to each other. The Court also reviewed the development of the concept of sustainable development in the International sphere. The Court referred to the Stockholm Declaration of 1972, Caring for Earth, 1991, the Earth Summit, and the Rio Declaration of 1992 and opined that the Precautionary Principle and the Polluter Pays Principle are indispensable features of Sustainable Development. In the case of **M C Mehta v. Kamal Nath** (1997) 1SCC 388 the Supreme Court reiterated the decision given in Vellore Citizen Welfare Forum case stating that the Precautionary Principle is a part of the environment law in India.

The Precautionary Principle was very comprehensively reviewed by the Apex Court in the case of **AP Control Pollution Board v. Prof. M V Nayadu** AIR 1999 SC 812. The Court stated that it is better to go wrong in taking caution and prevent environmental harm rather than waiting for the issue to materialize into an irreversible problem. The Court opined that the Precautionary Principle was evolved because of lack of scientific certainty only, and the principle involves anticipating the harm the environment may suffer and act on the basis of that. In the case of **Narmada Bachao Andolan v. UOI**, AIR 2000 SC 3751 the Apex Court very clearly laid down the proposition of law, and specifically of Precautionary Principle. The Court stated that when an issue pertains to environmental damage, the onus of proof is on the person who is contending that the activities carried on by him are not harmful to the environment. The party who is giving such contention also has to satisfy the Court of the same, that there will be no environmental degradation due to his activities.

Relationship between Environmental Protection and Economic Development

The progress of international environmental law reflects the close relationship between environmental protection and economic development. Thus there is a strong concern on the part of states to ensure that their economic interests are taken into account in the development and application of international environmental law. Laws adopted to protect the environment can impose significant costs. Moreover, certain developed countries will be placed to benefit from the adoption of stringent environmental standards, including the advantages gained from the sale of environmentally sound technology, while others will be concerned about the threat to their economic competitiveness which results from the failure of other countries to adopt similar stringent standards.

Most environmental treaties do not provide for financial resources to be made available to compensate for the additional costs of protective measures, partly because at the time of negotiations their economic consequences were not fully considered. For example, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species (CITES), 1973 does not provide compensation to African states resulting from the loss of revenue because of the ban on international trade in ivory. This may limit the desire of many developing states to support similar measures in future. There is also concern that the move towards harmonization of standards might lead to a lowering of environmental standards to ensure that economic costs can be borne as reflected in efforts to introduce a principle of “cost effectiveness” to guide decision making under some environmental agreements e.g., Climate Convention 1992 (Art. 3).

It is hardly surprising, therefore that in recent years environmental concerns have become economic concerns. Two issues have been particularly acute in recent negotiations : (i) Developing countries have sought to make their acceptance of environmental obligations depending upon the provision of financial assistance, and (ii) Some developing countries in order to prevent competitive economic disadvantages (which might flow from noncompliance) have striven to ensure that environmental treaties establish effective institution which can verify and ensure that the contracting parties comply with their environmental obligations.

Concept of Sustainable Development

The integration of environmental protection and economic development has led to the emergence of the concept of “sustainable development”. The concept of sustainable development may be found in many environmental treaties, expressly or impliedly, and other international instruments prior to the publication of the Brundtland Report in 1987. Nevertheless, the Brundtland Report is commonly viewed as the point at which sustainable development became a broad global policy objective and set the international community on a path which led to UNCED and the body of rules referred to as “International law in the field of sustainable development”, but distinguished from international environmental law.

The Brundtland Report defined sustainable development as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Two key concepts are contained with it : (i) The concept of ‘need’, in particular, the essential needs of the present generation, and (ii) the idea of limitations imposed by the stage of technology and social organization on the environment’s ability to meet present and future needs.

Growth by itself is not enough. High levels of productive activity and widespread poverty can coexist and can endanger the environment. Hence, sustainable development requires that societies must meet human needs both by increasing productive potential and by ensuring equitable opportunities for all and their non exploitation. Satisfaction of basic human needs (food, clothing, shelter, jobs) and aspirations for an improved quality of life of the vast number of people in the developing countries is the major objective of development. A world in which poverty and inequity are endemic will always be prone to ecological and other crises. Sustainable development, within a North-South framework places emphasis on social and economic objectives rather than ecological ones.

Conclusion

Today the planet faces a diverse and growing range of environmental challenges which can be addressed only through international cooperation. Acid rain, ozone depletion, climate change, loss of biodiversity, toxic and hazardous wastes, pollution of rivers and seas and depletion of fresh water resources are some of the issues

which international law is being called to address. These issues are complex, and cannot be addressed properly without taking account of political, cultural, economic and scientific concerns.

International environmental law comprises those substantive, procedural and institutional rules of international law which have as their primary objective the protection of the environment. But the term environment is not free from conceptual difficulty. The term has become stretched and distended with time, so that what it encompasses is a question for debate.

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